

An investigation on synthesis and photocatalytic properties of Eu-doped anatase TiO₂ coated magnetite

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Abstract : Preparation of Eu-doped anatase titanium dioxide (TiO₂) coated magnetite (Fe₃O₄) photocatalysts (Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄) and their photocatalytic properties under UV and visible light were reported. The composite photocatalysts were prepared by coating photoactive Eu/TiO₂ onto magnetic Fe₃O₄ through the hydrolysis of tetrabutyltitanate (Ti(OC₄H₉)₄) in water/oil (w/o) microemulsion with precursors of Eu(NO₃)₃ and Ti(OC₄H₉)₄ in the presence of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles. The morphological, structural and optical properties of the prepared samples were characterized by BET surface area, transmission electron microscopy (TEM), X-ray diffraction (XRD) and UV-Vis absorption spectroscopy. The effect of Eu ion content on the photocatalytic activity was studied, and the result revealed that 0.15 mol% Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ exhibited the highest photoactivity. The photocatalytic activities of prepared photocatalysts in UV and visible light were estimated by measuring the decomposition rate of phenol (50 mg/L) in an aqueous solution. The results showed that the prepared photocatalyst was activated by visible light and used as effective catalyst in photooxidation reactions. The photocatalytic performance of Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ was almost 3.0 times higher than that of single phase TiO₂ (either TiO₂ prepared by same method or Degussa P25) and TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ for degradation of phenol under visible light. In addition, the possibility of cyclic usage of the prepared photocatalyst was also confirmed. Moreover, the prepared composite exhibits paramagnetic behaviors at room temperature and could be easily recovered from the medium by a simple magnetic process. It can therefore be potentially applied for the treatment of water contaminated by organic pollutants.

Keywords : Titanium dioxide, magnetite, Eu-doping, photocatalytic activity.

Introduction

The heterogeneous photocatalysis has been proposed as an advanced oxidation process for the mineralization of various environmental organic pollutants in gas and liquid phases¹⁻³. Titanium dioxide (TiO₂) is one of the most studied semiconductors for photocatalytic reactions due to its high activity, chemical stability, robustness against photocorrosion, low toxicity and availability at low cost so far, especially for the detoxification of water and air⁴⁻⁸. The photocatalytic degradation systems using fine TiO₂ powder under UV irradiation have been widely investigated^{9,10}. However, practical applications of photocatalysis are limited because of at least two obvious problems arising from using fine TiO₂ powders : (i) separation of fine particles of TiO₂ used after the treatment process and the recycling of the photocatalyst; (ii) low photoefficiency¹¹. Many techniques were proposed for

the immobilization of fine TiO₂ on solid supports to eliminate the first problem¹²⁻¹⁵. In order to improve the photocatalytic activity of fine TiO₂ powders, many researches have been carried out. These results showed that selective metal ion doping was one of the effective means¹⁶⁻²¹, which could provide a framework to more easily incorporate the photocatalytic and solar efficiency of this material. Rare earth metals having incompletely occupied 4*f* and empty 5*d* orbitals often serve as catalyst or promote catalysis. Some results showed that the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ could be improved by the doping of some rare earth metals²²⁻²⁶. Besides, it has been proved that Eu ion, as one of the rare earth metals, has the ability to enhance the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂ due to the electrons trap effect supplied by the alterable chemical valence (Eu²⁺ and Eu³⁺) sites^{27,28}.

In the present work, a series of Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ com-

posites (Eu/TiO₂ coatings on Fe₃O₄) were prepared through the hydrolysis of Ti(OC₄H₉)₄ in microemulsion with precursors of Eu(NO₃)₃ and Ti(OC₄H₉)₄, where Fe₃O₄ was synthesized by co-precipitation of iron(II) and iron(III) in the presence of ammonium hydroxide²⁹. The photocatalytic activities of Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ in UV and visible light for the degradation of phenol were also investigated. The regeneration of TiO₂ photocatalyst is one of key steps to making heterogeneous photocatalysis technology for practical applications. The separation problem of the prepared photocatalyst has been solved, after photodegradation, the magnetic composite can be separated from the medium by a simple magnetic process³⁰, so the photocatalyst can be reused easily. Moreover, the activity of TiO₂ was not depressed by doping the magnetic photocatalyst with europium. It can therefore be potentially applied for the treatment of water contaminated by organic pollutants.

Experimental

Synthesis procedure :

Preparation of TiO₂ nanoparticles :

The preparation procedure of anatase TiO₂ was essentially the same as that described in our previous paper¹⁵. A solution was prepared as follows : 0.02 mol Ti(OC₄H₉)₄ (analytic grade, Shanghai Xingta Co., Ltd., China) was added to 50 mL anhydrous ethanol under vigorous stirring, whose acidity was adjusted with 0.1 mol/L HNO₃ to pH 2.5, then 0.01 mol triethylamine was added as a stabilizer, and the solution was stirred at 200 rpm for 2–3 min in an argon atmosphere. A second solution was prepared as follows : hydrochloric acid (1.0 mol/L, 3.0 mL) and water (0.72 mL) were added to anhydrous ethanol (50 mL) and mixed well by a magnetic stirrer at 200 rpm. The two solutions were then mixed together and stirred vigorously for 30 min under flowing argon. The TiO₂ sol formed is transparent, quite stable and highly sensitive to triethylamine and water, and subsequently kept at room temperature for five days until white powders were obtained. The resulting powders were dried for 96 h at 80 °C and then calcinated at 500 °C in an argon atmosphere for 2 h.

Preparation of Eu-doped TiO₂ nanoparticles :

Eu doping TiO₂ nanoparticles were synthesized using

almost the same method. The appropriate amount of Eu(NO₃)₃ was dissolved in anhydrous ethanol, which was added dropwise into the distilled water prior to the hydrolysis of Ti(OC₄H₉)₄ under vigorous stirring.

Preparation of Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles :

Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles were prepared by hydrolysis of Ti(OC₄H₉)₄ in w/o microemulsions consisting of cetyltrimethylammonium bromide (CTAB) as the surfactant, *n*-pentanol as the co-surfactant, cyclohexane as the oil phase. In a typical experimental procedure, the microemulsion solution was prepared by dissolving 2.0 g CTAB in 30 mL cyclohexane and 2 mL *n*-pentanol, which were stirred vigorously for 30 min until it became clear and transparent. A certain amount of Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles synthesized by chemical co-precipitation of iron(II) and iron(III) in the presence of ammonium hydroxide²⁹ was added to above microemulsion solution and sonicated for 30 min. HNO₃ aqueous solution (2.0 mol/L) was then added to adjust the microemulsion solution until pH was about 5–6. Then, 0.1 mol/L Ti(OC₄H₉)₄/anhydrous ethanol solution containing appropriate amount of Eu(NO₃)₃ was slowly added dropwise into the above microemulsion solution. After that, the reaction was kept by ultrasonic stirring for 10 h. The resulting precipitates were separated by centrifugation, washed repeatedly with ethanol, and dried at 60 °C for 24 h in air and further calcinated at 500 °C in an argon atmosphere for 2 h. The composition of the prepared samples were determined to be Eu : Fe₃O₄ : TiO₂ = 0.1 : 25 : 74.9 ~ 0.4 : 30 : 69.6.

Characterization :

The specific surface area and pore volumes of samples were obtained by nitrogen adsorption-desorption at 77 K using the BET method³¹ with a micromeritics 2000 instrument (ASAP 2000, Micromeritics, USA). The magnetic measurements were carried out with a vibrating sample magnetometer (VSM, Model 4500). The micrographs of the prepared samples were examined with a transmission electron microscopy (TEM, JEM 2000 EX). X-Ray diffraction (XRD) was used for identification of the crystalline phases of the prepared samples. The XRD patterns were recorded in the range of 2θ = 20–80° by step scanning with a Rigaku D/max-r B X-ray diffractometer using graphite monochromatic copper radiation (Cu-Kα) at 40 kV, 30 mA. UV-Vis adsorption

spectroscopy measurements were performed by using a UV-Vis diffuse reflectance spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV-2550). Reflectance spectra were referenced to BaSO₄.

Photocatalytic degradation studies :

The photocatalytic activities of the prepared catalysts in UV and visible light were estimated by measuring the degradation rate of phenol (50 mg/L) in an aqueous solution without concerning the degradation intermediates in detail. All the experiments in this study were triplicate. The results presented were the mean values with a total error of less than 5%.

UV irradiation :

Experiments were carried out using a magnetically stirred quartz reactor and a 20 W UV lamp with a maximum UV irradiation peak of 365 nm at ambient temperature of about 20 °C, 1.0 g photocatalyst was added under stirring into 500 mL of phenol whose initial concentration was 50 mg/L. Sixty-minute adsorption time in dark condition was allowed before the start of photoreactions. Then, samples of the suspension were withdrawn after a definite time interval, and the photocatalysts in the suspension were recovered by an external magnetic process. Then the samples were analyzed for residual phenol concentration using a UV-Vis spectrophotometer (UV762, Shanghai Analysis Co.). Dark controls were done for each series of experiments. To compare the photocatalytic activity of Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄, single phase TiO₂ (either TiO₂ prepared by same method or Degussa P25) and TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ powders were used as the reference systems. The Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ sample was used repeatedly, and each cycle lasted 4 h. Before the beginning of the next cycle, the remaining solution was replaced by fresh phenol solution with 50 mg/L.

Visible light irradiation :

The experiments with visible light irradiation were performed at ambient temperature of about 20 °C. 500 mL of 50 mg/L phenol aqueous solution and 1.0 g of photocatalyst were added in quartz reactor. Prior to illumination, the mixture was stirred 60 min in the dark to achieve the adsorption equilibrium. In the process of degradation, the reaction mixture was magnetically stirred. A 150 W metal halide lamp provided the light source. To limit the irradiation wavelength, the light beam was passed through a 410 nm cut filter (L41) to assure cut-off wave-

lengths shorter than 410 nm. Then, samples of the suspension were withdrawn after a definite time interval and recovered photocatalysts by an external magnetic process. Then the samples were analyzed for residual phenol concentration.

Results and discussion

Characterization :

The microstructure changes of pure Fe₃O₄, pure TiO₂ and Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ were listed in Table 1. As shown in Table 1, the deposited iron oxide contributed to a decrease in the N₂-BET surface area, mesoporous volume and microporous volume. As Fe₃O₄ has a relatively small surface area and microporous volume (63.7 m²/g and 0.011 cm³/g, respectively) its presence in the composites should cause a decrease in the surface area and microporous volume compared to pure TiO₂. The magnetic parameters such as saturation magnetization (*M_s*), coercivity (*H_c*) and remanent magnetization (*M_r*) were obtained from VSM experiments. The lower *M_s* of Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ (11.8 emu/g) is consistent with its less Fe₃O₄ content in unit weight sample. The low values of *H_c* and *M_r* (52.2 Oe and 1.9 emu/g, respectively) indicated that the prepared Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ sample exhibits paramagnetic behaviors at room temperature³², which makes the photocatalyst can be separated more easily by an applied magnetic filter^{29,33}.

Table 1. Microstructure of pure Fe₃O₄, pure TiO₂ and 0.15 mol% Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ photocatalyst

Sample	<i>S</i> _{BET} (m ² /g)	Mesoporous volume (cm ³ /g)	Microporous volume (cm ³ /g)
Fe ₃ O ₄	63.7	0.368	0.011
TiO ₂	158.6	0.753	0.062
Eu/TiO ₂ /Fe ₃ O ₄	134.8	0.637	0.058

A TEM micrograph of Fe₃O₄ was shown in Fig. 1(a). It could be seen from the micrograph that the nanoparticles aggregated into clusters. However, the size of the particles that formed the clusters was around 20 nm and very uniform. Fig. 1(b) shows the TEM micrograph of prepared Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄, from which we could see that the size of the composite particles was around 40 nm, and most TiO₂ was coated on the surface of Fe₃O₄ particles, which exhibits paramagnetic behaviors at room tempera-

ture, so the prepared $\text{Eu}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ particles could be separated completely by an applied magnetic filter (including the small part of TiO_2 not coated on the surface of Fe_3O_4).

Fig. 1. TEM micrograph of (a) Fe_3O_4 and (b) 0.15 mol% $\text{Eu}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$.

To obtain information on the crystal structure of the $\text{Eu}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ photocatalyst, X-ray diffraction patterns were measured. The XRD patterns of prepared magnetic samples were shown in Fig. 2. All samples prepared have the anatase structure, with no significant rutile component. Fig. 2(a) shows XRD pattern of the Fe_3O_4 , presenting the characteristic peaks of cubic spinel structure. It could also be seen from Fig. 2(c) and Fig. 2(d) that the Fe_3O_4 maintained cubic spinel structure. This illuminated that the magnetic properties of Fe_3O_4 were basically in-

Fig. 2. XRD patterns of samples : (a) Fe_3O_4 , (b) TiO_2 , (c) $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$, (d) 0.15 mol% $\text{Eu}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$.

variable. No characteristic peak of Eu oxide was found in the XRD patterns, this suggests that the Eu dopant is partly isomorphously substituted into the TiO_2 crystalline phases possibly forming a so called “amorphous to XRD” phase, i.e. a phase in which a great number of very fine and defective crystallites are probably present. This phase is below the detection limit of XRD.

UV-Vis absorption spectra analysis :

UV-Vis absorption spectra were used to characterize the light absorption ability of the prepared photocatalysts. Fig. 3 shows the UV-Vis absorption spectra that showed the influence of Eu ion on the UV-Vis absorption. Modification of $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ with Eu ion significantly affected the absorption properties of photocatalysts. Compared with

Fig. 3. UV-Vis absorption spectra of samples : (a) $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$, (b) 0.05 mol% $\text{Eu}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$, (c) 0.1 mol% $\text{Eu}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$, (d) 0.15 mol% $\text{Eu}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$.

$\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$, there was strong photoabsorption in the visible region for the Eu-doped photocatalysts. The red shift of the absorption edge implied a decrease in the band gap energy. The band gap energies (E_g) of the prepared photocatalysts were calculated by the formula $E_g = 1239.8/\lambda_g$ from the wavelength values corresponding to the intersection point of the vertical and horizontal parts of the spectra (λ_g)³⁴. For $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$, the E_g was 3.21 eV. In the case of Eu-doped $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ photocatalysts, the band gap energies of 0.05 mol%, 0.10 mol% and 0.15 mol% $\text{Eu}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ are 3.08 eV, 2.93 eV and 2.78 eV, respectively. The narrowing of band gaps of the prepared

Eu-doped samples might be resulted from the modification of the electronic structure around the conduction band edge of TiO₂. For pure TiO₂, the absorption in the ultraviolet range ($\lambda = 378$ nm) was associated with the excitation of the O 2*p* electron to the Ti 3*d* level. The red shift of the absorption spectrum can be ascribed to the charge transfer between the TiO₂ valence or conduction band and the Eu ion 4*f* level²³. As a result, the Eu-doped samples have trapping level which decreased the TiO₂ band gap. Moreover, because of rare earth elements possessing a broad absorption band, the effect of those incorporated into the TiO₂ was similar to adding a photosensitizer to the reaction solution. Therefore, the Eu ions surrounding the TiO₂ grains could absorb a larger range of light radiation, which brought about the higher light absorption in the 420–700 nm region of the Eu-doped samples³⁵.

Effect of Eu-doped content on the photocatalytic activity of Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ :

Fig. 4 shows the results of phenol degradation with irradiation time under UV irradiation in the presence of Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ with Eu-doped content in the range of 0.05–0.25 mol%. It was shown that the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ enhanced after Eu-doping, the optimum content of Eu-doping was 0.15 mol%. It was

Fig. 4. Degradation curves of phenol with UV irradiation time.

considered that the presence of the Eu ions on the TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ particles influenced the photocatalytic activity by altering the electron-hole pair recombination rate through

the following process^{28,36} :

Thus, the increase of the photocatalytic activity with the increase of the content of Eu-doping might be attributed to the electrons trapped in Eu sites, which were subsequently transferred to the absorbed O₂. The photoactivity of the catalyst increased gradually with the content of Eu-doping when the content of Eu-doping was lower than 0.15 mol%. However, the photoactivity of the catalyst decreased when the content of Eu-doping reached 0.2 mol% meaning that high doping might make the dopants as the recombination centers of the photoexcited electrons, thus the photocatalytic activity was reduced.

The UV-Vis absorption spectra showed that Eu-doping improved the ultraviolet absorption and the red-shift of the absorption profile, which was benefited to improve the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂/Fe₃O₄. It was known from the photocatalytic mechanism that oxygen adsorbed on photocatalyst could trap effectively the photogenerated electron³⁷, so the simple recombination between electron and hole was inhibited. The redox probability increased, and the photocatalytic activity enhanced.

Photocatalytic activity :

Photocatalytic activities of the prepared samples were estimated by measuring the degradation rate of phenol in the presence of UV and visible light irradiation without concerning the degradation intermediates in detail. Pure TiO₂ synthesized by the sol-gel method and Degussa P25 were used as the references. The amount of TiO₂ or Degussa P25 chosen is 1.0 g/L, which is adequate under our conditions without disturbing the UV light entering the reactor. It was found that phenol concentration remained stable (36–39 mg/L) after 1 h of stirring without illumination in the presence of obtained powders.

Fig. 4 shows the results of phenol degradation with irradiation time under UV irradiation in the presence of different samples. The results revealed two main observations : (i) the activity of the TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ particles was lower than that of single phase TiO₂ samples (pure TiO₂ or Degussa P25); (ii) the Eu-doping of TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ resulted in higher photoactivity than pure TiO₂, Degussa P25 and TiO₂/Fe₃O₄. The red-shift of the absorption spec-

trum was observed obviously and the ultraviolet absorption was increased in the $\text{Eu}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ (Fig. 3), showing that Eu-doping improved photoutilization of TiO_2 , through separating the produced electrons and holes, and reducing their recombination rate, which helps to improve the photocatalytic activity of TiO_2 .

The lower photoactivity of $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ compared to the pure TiO_2 prepared by the same method and Degussa P25 could be ascribed to the electronic interactions between the two semiconductors, which has been described by others³⁸⁻⁴⁰. Electronic interactions occurred at the point of contact of the different phases (heterojunction), leading to the transfer of charge carriers across this junction when two or more semiconductors are in contact³². So the photogenerated charge carriers in the excited TiO_2 could be transferred to Fe_3O_4 phase because of the lower lying conduction band and upper lying valence band of Fe_3O_4 particles⁴¹, so the charge transfer process to adsorbed substance was unfavorable during light illumination, the photocatalytic activity was reduced. The narrower band gap of Fe_3O_4 (0.1 eV) was also favorable to lead to an increase in the recombination of electron and hole which subsequently lower the photoactivity of $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ ⁴¹. In addition, when Fe_3O_4 is present in the catalyst, less TiO_2 is present, especially if the structure is not a well core-shell, so the photocatalytic activity with the Fe_3O_4 present is lower than that of the pure TiO_2 prepared by the same method or Degussa P25.

Fig. 5. Degradation curves of phenol with visible light irradiation time.

Photocatalytic activities of different samples under visible light were shown in Fig. 5. It could be observed that the $\text{Eu}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ showed the best photocatalytic performance, and its photocatalytic performance is almost 3.0 times higher than that of $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ for degradation of phenol under visible light. From the UV-Vis absorption spectra of samples (Fig. 3), it could be seen that the intensity and region of visible light photoabsorption on Eu-doped samples was stronger and larger, respectively than those of $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$. The strong absorption is beneficial to the photocatalytic activity because the available photons are proportional to photoabsorption. So, the Eu-doped $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ exhibited higher photocatalytic activity than pure $\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$.

Fig. 6. The cyclic performance of $\text{Eu}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ under UV irradiation.

Cyclic performances of $\text{Eu}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ for the degradation of phenol :

In order to test the cyclic performance for the $\text{Eu}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$ photocatalyst, the photocatalytic degradation experiments of phenol had been repeated for 3 cycles. The change in relative degradation percentage of phenol with cycling operation was shown in Fig. 6. It was observed that phenol could be degraded rapidly by the present photocatalyst under UV irradiation. The photocatalytic activity of the present photocatalyst was just slightly reduced in stirred aqueous solution, and the $\text{Eu}/\text{TiO}_2/\text{Fe}_3\text{O}_4$, after being used four times, remained about 89% of photocatalytic activity of the fresh sample. The degradation of phenol could reach 85.58% when the irradiation time

was 4 h, it was slightly lower than that for fresh P25. Thus it is suggested that the deposited anatase TiO₂ has firmly attached to the Fe₃O₄ surface, and can not be easily exfoliated from the Fe₃O₄ with mechanically stirred solutions for a long period. At the same time, it also proved that the final removal of phenol from solution was caused by the photocatalytic degradation other than the adsorption process that will lead to saturated adsorption of phenol on the photocatalyst. These results indicated that cyclic usage of the Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ composite was possible and its stability in treating polluted water was satisfactory. Therefore, it is potentially employable for continuous photocatalytic degradation processes.

Conclusions :

A composite photocatalyst of Eu-doped anatase titanium dioxide coated magnetite (Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄) was successfully prepared by depositing Eu-doped titanium dioxide onto the magnetite through the hydrolysis of tetrabutyltitanate in w/o microemulsion. The photocatalyst thus prepared was applied to degrade model contaminated water of phenol. The results showed that the photocatalytic activity of TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ enhanced after Eu-doping, and 0.15 mol% Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ exhibited optimum photocatalytic activity for phenol degradation. The Eu-doping caused absorption spectra of TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ to shift to the visible region. The prepared Eu/TiO₂/Fe₃O₄ sample exhibits paramagnetic behaviors at room temperature, so the photocatalyst could be separated more easily by an applied magnetic filter and reused without any mass loss. The degradation percentage of phenol was still higher than 85% as the photocatalyst was used for four times.

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